

Use of Natural Zeolite for Ammonia Removal during Simulated Transport of Live Juvenile Sea Bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*)

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the effects of zeolites on total ammonia nitrogen (TAN) removal during a 24-hour-sea bass transportation. Five experimental treatments (0 (control), 10, 20, 30 and 40 g/L zeolite) with 3 replications were tried in 14 L plastic tanks. To each tank 90 sea bass (total weight 175.07 ± 0.49 g) were stocked. The zeolites were put in mesh bags and renewed after 8th and 16th hours (hrs) after transfer started. TAN contents of tank waters were measured at 8th, 16th and 24th hrs. The results revealed that at 8th hrs 20, 30 and 40 g/L zeolite doses were significantly effective compared with the control. At 16th and 24th hrs the lowest zeolite level (10 g/L) was also effective in TAN removal. In general highest TAN removal was achieved with 40 g/L treatment with efficiencies of 18.33%, 34.08% and 20.96% at 8th, 16th and 24th hrs respectively. Overall, the results suggest that the use of zeolite in sea bass transportation could bring remarkable benefits and thereby increase fish transportation density and welfare.